

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

COMUNES: NEW FARC IN AN OLD
COLOMBIA?

Author: Flávia Osorio

POLICY STATEMENT

The FARC (Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia), used the same acronym in August 2017 to define its new political name - “Alternative Revolutionary Force of the Common” - and a red rose as a logo, evoking the social-democratic symbols, after its demobilization as an armed group. In January 2021, it officially changed its name to “Comunes”, at its 2nd National Assembly, which took place in the city of Medellín.

The claim for such a change is that FARC is a name already stigmatized and that its maintenance after the demobilization of the guerrillas generated resistance in the population. According to its leaders, this change is a “real and transformative bet for peace” in Colombia. Its members believe that the change will revolve its already scratched image, putting the party back in the running for the 2022 legislative elections. This is what we will look into this Policy Brief.

BACKGROUND

The FARC, a Colombian guerrilla group founded in 1964, demobilized in November 2016, after the peace negotiations that took place during the government of President Juan Manuel Santos (2010-2018). They then assumed the character of a political party, granting with the demobilization, 5 seats in the Senate and 5 seats in the House of Representatives for two consecutive electoral periods.

In the 2018 legislative elections, they obtained around 50 thousand votes. Since then, there have been a series of divisions among its members: some have sought the path of social democracy, as a way of easing the association of the new party with its guerrilla past; others wanted to maintain the previous revolutionary mode. And today, mainly after the murder of several deserted members, dissident factions are still armed under the original name of the FARC and spread across different parts of Colombian territory financed by illegal mining, drug trafficking and kidnappings.

With the announcement by Iván Márquez of reincorporation, in mid-2019, the dissidents that occupied 53 municipalities, now occupy 85. With the change of name, the party ratified its commitment to peace, inviting the country to a national “pact”, integral, multisectoral, participatory and democratic political system, capable of definitively excluding weapons from politics”.

It is worth remembering that the FARC has already gone through other unsuccessful peace negotiations during the 20th century. Despite the negative result of the popular referendum with a view to endorsing the peace negotiations in October 2016, Santos received the Nobel Peace Prize, the government and the guerrillas decided to return to the negotiations and the decision to endorse them was granted by Congress. Four years after the referendum, in this year of 2021, the JEP (Special Jurisdiction for Peace) formally accused the guerrillas of war crimes and against humanity, which brings a new, but expected, political context to Colombia.

FINDINGS

It is interesting to note that what is happening in Colombia at the current juncture is very similar to the current political polarization in Brazil, the United States and other countries in the world, in which groups of the most diverse political hues, self-called “progressive” seek to unite to, en bloc, to oppose the conservative and right-wing groups that established themselves in power in the last elections.

The “Comunes” speech that this is the right moment for “creating a great coalition of forces with all the democrats of the country”, uniting sectors that “fight for change and building a single front against authoritarianism” and a “True equality before the law and the rights of citizens”, is a discourse that has been repeated frequently in the American continent, in both countries mentioned above. In addition, with the JEP's formal accusation that the former FARC is responsible for more than 21,000 kidnappings, murders, torture, sexual violence and forced displacement of people in Colombia, the name change strategy comes in handy, in an attempt to untie his image from the fratricidal war that left more than 250 thousand dead in the country.

That said, new and fresh, and a possibility of lesser rejection of the new party by the population, since, now, it is understood that former combatants will be held accountable, the execution of sentences, the reparation of victims and, consequently, justice. It remains to be seen whether those incorporated into political life will be willing to suffer the penalties of the law (even under special conditions) and not to be co-opted by the dissident factions.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the Santos government's peace agreement have a characteristic very similar to that of the 1984 *Acuerdos de La Uribe*: when the Patriotic Union was formed for the transition of combatants to political life, many of its members were murdered. What has been seen in Colombia since the last agreement was the successive deaths of former guerrillas, who now number more than 200.

Political violence and harsh polarization has historically been and is part of Colombia's political life. Therefore, it is understood that it would be quite difficult for the Colombian population to accept an amnesty for former guerrillas along the lines set out before the popular referendum. The negative result of the referendum itself worsened political and legal instability in the country, although it ended the civil war in Colombia, regarding to FARC.

SUGGESTIONS

Given the above and the possibility of a less polarized political scenario in Colombia, it is suggested:

- 1) That the members of the Comunes take responsibility for the maintenance of the group and submit themselves to the penalties of the law and of the eventual condemnatory criminal decisions so that it survives as a political party and may have some chance to assist in the peace process and stand out in the next elections;
- 2) That the former combatants deliver all the goods for reparation to the victims, since until then only 4% of the inventoried goods have been returned, whose total inventory amounts to approximately US \$ 11.5 million (R\$ 65.7 million) and whose delivery and application deadline has already expired in December 2020;
- 3) The maintenance of the transitional justice process in the sphere of the Executive Power, whose composition has the character of administrative justice composed of renowned magistrates and jurists, including foreigners and whose conclusions are submitted to the Judiciary Power, for judgment.

REFERENCES

- (01) BOTERO, S. (2017). El Plebiscito y los desafíos políticos de consolidar la paz negociada em Colombia. https://scielo.conicyt.cl/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0718-090X2017000200369. Accessed: 3MAR2021.
- (02) OSORIO, F.M.S. (2016). Estado, Segurança e Paramilitarismo na Colômbia. Dissertação (Mestrado em Estudos Estratégicos). INEST, Universidade Federal Fluminense. Niterói, p. 174. 2016.
- (03) EL UNIVERSAL. (2021). El partido de las Farc cambió su nombre a 'Comunes'. <https://www.eluniversal.com.co/colombia/el-partido-de-las-farc-cambio-su-nombre-a-comunes-CJ4083051>. Accessed: 03MAR2021.
- (04) NOTÍCIAS UOL (2021). Tribunal de paz dá passo histórico na Colômbia e acusa as Farc por sequestros. <https://noticias.uol.com.br/ultimas-noticias/afp/2021/01/28/tribunal-de-paz-da-passo-historico-na-colombia-e-acusa-as-farc-por-sequestros.htm>. Accessed: 02MAR2021.
- (05) O GLOBO. (2020). Colombianos protestam contra assassinatos de ex-guerrilheiros das Farc. <https://oglobo.globo.com/mundo/colombianos-protestam-contra-assassinatos-de-ex-guerrilheiros-das-farc-24272642>. Accessed: 02MAR2021.
- (06) VANGUARDIA (2021). Farc solo entregaron el 4 % de bienes inventariados para reparar a víctimas <https://www.vanguardia.com/colombia/farc-solo-entregaron-el-4-de-bienes-inventariados-para-reparar-a-victimas-CB3407260>. Accessed: 04MAR2021.
- (07) CONGRESO DE COLOMBIA. Acto Legislativo 01 de 4 de abril del 2017. <https://dapre.presidencia.gov.co/normativa/normativa/ACTO%20LEGISLATIVO%20N%C2%B0%2001%20DE%204%20DE%20ABRIL%20DE%202017.pdf>